

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as
the new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 8.3

H - POPD - Requirement No. 3

v1.5: Correction of v1.4

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PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Cl: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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SUMMARY

This document corresponds to D8.3: H - POPD - Requirement No. 3.

According to the NEWSERA Grant Agreement, the next information is presented:

- The **informed consent procedures** that were implemented for the participation of humans.
- **Templates of the informed consent/assent forms** and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants).
- To meet **inclusiveness**, for **children** involved in the research, details on how their assent and the consent of the legal representatives were acquired. An analogous procedure was applied for **vulnerable adults**.
- The template applied for informed consent given by parents/legal guardians, in the case of attendance of infants and young children, clearly not as participants but present at physical encounters because they are in the care of their parents. The protection of their image (in recordings or photos) was the subject of this report.

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1. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CitSciComm	Citizen Science Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
FB	FormicaBlu
H	Human beings
IBERCIVIS	Fundación IBERCIVIS
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova

Table 1: Acronyms used in deliverable D8.3 H - POPD - Requirement No. 3

2. Introduction

As in every citizen science project, in NEWSERA, **each participant plays a central role**. Within citizen science, the participation of human beings does not entail them being the object of research - but rather them being co-creators of the research together with other stakeholders. In any case, the development of participatory methodologies in which citizen scientists are voluntarily involved through a non-contractual relationship implies rigorous protection of their rights regarding their data, particularly personal data.

D8.3: H - POPD - Requirement No. 3. presents the following information according to the NEWSERA Grant Agreement (pp.38-39) to comply with Personal Data Protection:

- The **informed consent procedures** that will be implemented for the participation of humans within the project.
- **Templates of the informed consent/assent forms** and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) to do so.
- To meet **inclusiveness**, for **children** involved in the research, details on how their assent (as a first step in their recruitment) and the consent of the legal representatives (as a second step in the children's recruitment) will be acquired. An analogous procedure will be applied for vulnerable adults.

All stakeholders will benefit from an improved communication within the science domain as a way to get in contact with other stakeholders and achieve their specific objectives. All kinds of tools, channels, platforms and media at all levels will be analysed and used as needed in order to increase engagement and outreach from an **inclusive perspective**, considering dimensions such as **gender, age, socio-cultural realities, territorial context or environment**. Data will be open, following the **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach**, particularly the culture and practices of Open Access in the wide framework of Open Science.

Depending on the progress of the **health situation in each country due to the COVID-19 crisis**, the number of participants, as well as the methodologies, will be decided on a country-by-country basis for each participative #CitSciComm Lab. In case these Labs are developed online, it will be ensured that all participants receive the necessary **information sheets**, and **informed consents** and those will be **properly collected and stored**.

3. Informed consent procedures

This section includes the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans, who are seen as - indeed - researchers along the whole process of the NEWSERA development.

For offline participatory methods, such as the #CitSciComm Labs (if feasible), information sheets and informed consents will be printed out and distributed to participants (to be collected and properly stored). Participants will be informed on the use that NEWSERA will do of their Personal Data at the very beginning of their involvement thoroughly. In the case of online Labs, due to COVID-19 pandemic, online consents provided will also be properly collected and stored. Information sheets and informed consents forms will be included in all the project digital tools.

Deliverable D8.2 POPD Requirement No. 2 includes more details on POPD participants.

3.1 Informed consent procedure for the survey on ‘Science Communication through Citizen Science’

The participation within the survey on ‘Science Communication through citizen science’ (launched on June 8th, 2020) required the informed consent of the participants. The reason for that is respondents were asked to voluntarily provide a contact email, but only in case they wanted to be informed about the survey results and/or in case they were interested in participate in the #CitSciComm Labs. This not mandatory question was asked at the very end of the survey. The rest of the survey contents were totally focused on the features of the projects which were interesting for NEWSERA research outcomes.

To achieve participation in the survey different means were used. Those means are detailed in Deliverable 8.1 in section 3.1 on research participants.

Those who voluntarily accessed the survey page were given all the relevant information (see figure below) to be able both to carry out the survey with their informed consent and to exercise all their rights in this respect.

Potential respondents could access the survey page, managed by partners at UNIPD, directly through the link or indirectly through the NEWSERA website, managed by partners FB. In both cases they had available all the necessary information on the activity and their rights in terms of POPD.

As part of NEWSERA, we are launching a survey about **communication in citizen science projects**. It's addressed to those responsible for citizen science projects based in the European Union and the United Kingdom: if you fit this description, we would like to hear about your experience!

The survey starts on June 8th and will end on June 26th. Completing the survey will give you the opportunity to participate, expenses covered, to our **#CitSciComm Labs** together with science communication experts and journalists. The Labs will consist in small group meetings, aimed at

Figure 1: Page of Newsera website to access to the survey, through UNIPD. Available at: <https://newsera2020.eu/2020/06/08/survey/>

Figure 2: Page of UNIPD to directly access the survey. Available at: <https://websurvey.unipd.it/survey/index.php/816644?lang=en>

The entire corresponding text is here transcribed, highlighting in bold the way to manifest **the informed consent to participate in the survey**.

Welcome! You just landed on the NEWSERA survey about science communication practices as performed by citizen science projects across the European Union and the UK. We are a European consortium funded by the H2020 programme, studying citizen science as a new form of science communication that can strengthen the link between science and society.

If you manage a citizen science project in any discipline area you are the expert we are looking for. We will ask some questions about your project, the way it involves citizens and it shares its results across society and within communities of practitioners. Completing the survey will give you the opportunity to participate, expenses covered, to our co-creation Labs together with science communication experts and journalists. The Labs will consist of

small group meetings, aimed at better understanding and improving science communication through a mutual learning process.

The questionnaire will take about 15 minutes to be filled in. You are free to leave the survey at any moment and to resume it later just by clicking on the button "Resume later" on the top left of the page.

The results of this survey will be published as aggregated statistical data and will be processed in accordance with art.13 of the 2016/679 European Regulation. Data will be stored and protected by the University of Padova in its servers. **By clicking on the "NEXT" button, your consent to the processing of personal data is implied pursuant to art. 13 of the European Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).** If you complete and submit the survey, keep in mind that, since all personal data are regulated under the GDPR, you can exercise your rights according to this law. You can request the complete elimination of your data by emailing to ethics@ibercivis.es. For any further detail please have a look at **NEWSERA Survey Privacy Notice** or write an e-mail to info@newsera2020.eu.

Annex in section 6 contains the **NEWSERA Survey Privacy Notice**.

3.2 Informed consent procedures for the #CitSciComm Labs and interviews

At the time we are presenting the current deliverable, the #CitSciComm Labs have not started yet. The emergence of the COVID-19 crisis have delayed their celebration, as well as involved their re-design to ensure the health and safety of all participants. To date, the information published about the Labs is contained on the NEWSERA website (<https://newsera2020.eu/labs/>).

Although the celebration of the Labs has been postponed from June to October 2020 (in principle online and/or in combination with offline meetings if possible), potential participants have already expressed their interest in being involved. **Many of the respondents to the survey have voluntarily provided their contact details when completing the survey.** Details on the criteria to identify/recruit research participants are included in Deliverable D8.1 H Requirement No 1, section 3.1.

As indicated in that document, during the development of the Labs, participants will be requested to participate in interviews and/or recordings for providing information on the NEWSERA research topic on citizen science and science communication (opinions, experiences, explanations, etc.). The research is not related to sensitive information (health, political ideology, religion, etc.) and does not require any biological sample from participants.

Information sheets and informed consents forms are included in all project digital tools. For the #CitSciComm Labs, informed consents will be printed out and distributed to participants (to be collected and properly stored).

Participants will be informed on the use that NEWSERA will do of their Personal Data at the very beginning of their involvement thoroughly. In case of conducting online Labs, due to COVID-19 pandemic, consents will also be properly collected and stored.

In subsection 5.1 of this deliverable, the contents of the information sheets that will be used in each one of the **activities in NEWSERA** project are presented: the **#CitSciComm Labs**, the **interviews** along with the possibility of **photographing and recording**. This information is necessary to obtain proper **informed consents**. Subsection 5.2 contains the corresponding **informed consent/assent forms**.

Deliverable D8.2 POPD Requirement No. 2 includes more details on POPD participants.

3.3 Reshaping of #CitSciComm Labs due to the COVID-19 pandemic

Considering the applications already received for the participation in the Labs as well as the projects related to NEWSERA which have demonstrated interest in joining the project, a list of participants will be elaborated for each country and at European level. Depending on the progress of the health situation in each country due to the COVID-19 crisis, the number of participants, as well as the methodologies, will be decided on a country-by-country basis for each Lab.

Thus, offline meetings will be restricted at the moment, and online tools and means to carry out project actions will be provided. Through collaborative platforms, which will be aligned with security and under the POPD NEWSERA policy, it will be possible to carry out combined activities, online and offline, if necessary.

4. An inclusive approach

4.1 Inclusiveness

As it is explained in the GA (p.81), NEWSERA promotes the co-design of innovative strategies in science communication. WP3 oversees the achievement of this objective by providing a space for targeted stakeholders involved in citizen science. In order to co-design those innovative strategies, *#CitSciComm Labs (addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders: citizen scientists, policy makers, career scientists, industry and SMEs; together with data and science journalists)* will be developed. From a bottom-up perspective, these actions will contribute to open up science and innovation broadly to the whole society and improve formal and informal teaching in science communication. The actions will also contribute to advance knowledge in science communication, by analyzing and demonstrating the concepts of Citizen Science Communication

and Citizen Data Journalism. **All stakeholders will benefit** from improved communication in science as a way to get in contact with other stakeholders and find a common agenda. All kinds of tools, channels, platforms, media and at all levels will be analysed and used as needed in order to increase engagement and outreach from an **inclusive perspective**, considering dimensions such as **gender, age, socio-cultural level, territorial context or environment**. Data will be open, using the **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach**, particularly the culture and practices of [Open Access](#) in the wide framework of Open Science.

The configuration of the working groups of each of the #CitSciComm Labs should be balanced, of course in terms of gender, but also of the different socio-economic and cultural realities, etc., that the people interested in participating have expressed.

4.2 Children, young people and vulnerable adults

As explained in deliverable 7.1 on DMP, children and young minors could be involved in activities, due the close connection between citizen science and **STEM/STEAM** education, which involves **Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics**, along with **Arts** and creativity.

Children and young people, with a particular **emphasis on girls**, can participate in some of the activities. Some **teachers** are **strongly motivated by STEAM training** and the need to encourage **critical thinking**. This attitude helps people - and especially those in the early stages of their training - to be **freer and more responsible**. Contact with representatives of the quadruple helix includes very significantly those working in **youth education and training**, and in particular in STEAM education. In addition, every teacher is a communicator and must also aim to become a communicator for students. The **synergies** between **science education, citizen science and journalism** will be the key for the educational community to be present in the activities of NEWSERA.

In this section we include details on how they assent as well as the consent of legal representatives are provided. NEWSERA will similarly proceed in case of **vulnerable adults**. The double objective is to **promote maximum inclusiveness, together with maximum protection of privacy of each singular person**.

The **Protection of Personal Data** will be guaranteed through the actions explained in deliverables included in WP8. Specifically the deliverable **D8.2 Report on POPD Requirement No. 2** together with this **D8.3 Report on H-POPD Requirement No. 3**, which will include data sharing, data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction of personal data, as well as templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants).

5. Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets

In this section, the contents of the templates that will be used in each project action including human participants are presented. Participants are considered as co-researchers in NEWSERA, as stated elsewhere.

At the moment this deliverable is presented, the survey on 'Science Communication through Citizen Science' has been launched as one of the activities including human participation within NEWSERA. Information regarding data privacy is presented below.

Regarding the #CitSciComm Labs and interviews - including taking photographs and recording - the drafts of templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets are shown.

As stated before, the delay and redesign of face-to-face activities due to the COVID-19 pandemic oblige us to reformulate the forms and information sheets. Therefore, the drafts on the above mentioned issues are presented, including the main points related to guaranteeing informed consent of all the stakeholders.

5.1 Information sheets

The contents of the information sheets that will be used in each one of the **activities within NEWSERA entailing human participation** are presented: the **#CitSciComm Labs**, the **interviews** along with the possibility of **photographing and recording**. This information is necessary to obtain proper informed consent.

Information Document:

- *Why the person has been invited to participate*
- *What he/she will have to do if he/she decides to take part*
- *What will be the risks of taking part of it*
- *How to withdraw from the project*
- *What we will do with their DATA*

NEWSERA activities.**Information sheet on Protection of Personal Data (POPD)****Dear participant,**

You are willing to participate in NEWSERA, a citizen science communication project based on co-creation to improve science communication through citizen science, by using a bottom-up approach (starting from the citizens) and involving quadruple-helix stakeholders: (1) policy makers, (2) academic scientists, (3) industries and SMEs, and (4) citizens, together with science communicators and data and science journalists. Before taking part, and having understood the purpose of the project explained in this information document, it is essential to us that you understand which personal data we are collecting and how we will be treating this information. Please, read this document carefully. If you have any doubt or something is unclear to you, please ask any of the project partners, face-to-face when possible, or by email at ethics@ibercivis.es.

Purpose of the project

The overall objective of NEWSERA is to show the possibilities of citizen science as an inclusive, broad and powerful channel of scientific communication. Citizen science allows for increased trust in scientific communication and, in turn, in science in general. While opening up science and innovation to the whole society, citizen science improves scientific training and promotes critical thinking, reducing the spreading and production of fake news.

Our challenge is to demonstrate the virtues of citizen science as a tool for scientific communication, defining specific strategies together with quadruple helix stakeholders - that is policy makers, academic scientists, industries and SMEs, and citizens, together with science communicators and data and science journalists.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You have been invited to participate to NEWSERA: [1] as a member of one of the stakeholder groups following the quadruple helix model; [2] or as an expert in science communication; [3] or as a science or data journalist [PLEASE INSERT HERE YOUR GROUP]

What will I have to do if I decide to take part?

You can contribute, as the other researchers, sharing your knowledge, experience and opinions through the #CitSciComm Labs and interviews, offline and/or online. You can also accept to be recorded and photographed during an interview or alongside the Labs activities.

As for your ethical duties, you will not behave in an unethical way, that is, you will not communicate fake information with bad faith.

What will be the risks of taking part of it?

Regarding potential risks, those do not exceed in probability or magnitude the ones that could be expected in a work activity based on agreed meetings (physical and/or online), in which experiences and knowledge are discussed and shared around common projects.

Participation in this project is entirely voluntary and unpaid. Meals are covered as well as travel expenses when it is necessary to move from one city to another.

How to withdraw from the project?

You can withdraw from the project anytime you decide it, by email to ethics@ibercivis.es, or by mail to Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro Edificio I+D C, C/ Mariano Esquillor Gómez, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza (Spain). You do not need to add any explanation of why you want to withdraw from the project.

What will we do with your DATA?

All personal data is regulated under the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GRPD). You can erase all your personal data from all project platforms at any time. You can also download all the data that you have provided to the project. You can also be part of audio/video recording or photographs which might be used only to document and disseminate the project activities, if you specifically consent.

Your personal data will be used only for:

If it is previously accepted, contact you to inform you about new events specifically related to NEWSERA, or advances on the project.

Who is responsible for data processing?

Ibercivis is responsible for processing all personal - and no personal - data obtained. Ibercivis is a non-profit private foundation with NIF: G99330094. It was created on November 14, 2011 in Madrid. Its objectives are to continue its work of collaboration with citizen science research and carry out dissemination and training activities. It has a fiscal address in Campus Río Ebro, R&D Building, C/ Mariano Esquillor s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain.

Personal data transfer

We follow strict security procedures when storing personal data. Under no circumstances we will transfer personal data to third parties.

Rights and how to exercise them. You have the right to:

- Request information about whether we have personal data about you and, if so, what information we have, why we have it and how we are using it.
- Request access to your personal data. This allows you to receive a copy of your personal data and to correct any incomplete or incorrect information.
- Request personal data deletion. This allows you to delete or ask us to delete your personal data.
- Request to transfer your personal data to you or to a third party in an electronic and structured format - commonly known as the right to data portability.
- You can exercise any of these rights by email to ethics@ibercivis.es.
- You will not have to pay any fee to access your personal data - or to exercise any other of your rights.

5.2 Informed consent/assent forms

The contents of the informed consent/assent forms that will be used in each of the activities in NEWSERA, both online and offline, are presented as follows:

5.2.1 Template Consent form for participating in #CitSciComm Labs and interviews (both general and vulnerable persons)

The first one is the template informed consent form addressed to adults capable of giving their consent.

Template Consent form for participating in CitSciComm Labs and/or interviews

Dear participant,

After having read the **POPD information document**, please fill in the next form.

Issue	Yes	No
I have read the information presented in the POPD information document provided by the NEWSERA project		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
I know the possibility to ask any doubt regarding the project using face-to-face interview, if possible, or by email at ethics@ibercivis.es		
I know that I am doing voluntary contributions and I can leave the project when I want		
I will not upload fake data with bad faith		
I know that my personal data is regulated under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GRPD)		
I agree to take part in this project		

Name and Surname

Signature

Date

Ibercivis, as NEWSERA data responsible, is committed to processing information in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The personal data collected on this form will be held securely and will only be used for administrative purposes.

Your rights

You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about you and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required. You can ask Ibercivis to stop using your images/recordings at any time, in which case it will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation.

Contact details

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information please contact with Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. If you have any questions relating to data protection please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer, Francisco Sanz, tel: +34 876 55 53 96 email ethics@ibercivis.es

There is a different form in case of vulnerable persons - **children, young people or vulnerable adults** - are involved in some of the activities. In these cases the form is adapted in order to ensure the total understanding of their contents, although it will have to be signed by an authorized representative.

There are two steps and the corresponding forms:

- First step/form: to be completed by the child, young person or vulnerable Adult.
- Second step/form: to be completed by the legal representative, parent or guardian.

First step

Oral information will be given to the **child/young person/vulnerable adult** about the NEWSERA project and the activities in which they are involved, adapting the language according to its development and understanding. Information will be provided in terms similar to the next ones.

There is scientific research in which citizens actively participate, e.g. observing butterflies and taking notes in a field notebook, classifying images of galaxies on a website, or photographing disease-producing mosquitoes, etc. This type of research is called citizen science.

NEWSERA is a project that aims to improve the communication of science and citizen science, so that the organisers and the people who participate can transmit their knowledge very well to many different people in society.

In NEWSERA, the participation and opinion of many people is important, so that, between all of us, we can make science better understood and known. Therefore, we would like to count on your participation in the workshops and activities of the project.

Form to be completed by the Child/ Young person/Vulnerable Adult

Issue	Yes	No
I have understood what the project is about and in which activities I can be involved.		
I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and what I will be doing.		
I voluntarily agree to participate in the NEWSERA activity/event.		
I know I can leave the activity/event when I want.		

Name and Surname

Signature

Date

Second step

The POPD information document and informed consent form will be provided to the **Representative/Parent/Guardian of the vulnerable person**.

Template consent form for participating in CitSciComm Labs and/or interviews (vulnerable persons)

Dear participant representative,

After having read the **POPD information document**, please fill in the next form.

Issue	Yes	No
I have read the information presented in the POPD information document provided by the NEWSERA project.		
Both myself and the person I represent have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the activity, using face-to-face interview if possible, or by email at ethics@ibercivis.es		
Both myself and the person I represent know that she/he is doing voluntary contributions and can leave the activity/event when they want.		
I know that the personal data of the person I represent is regulated under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).		
The person I represent agrees to participate in the NEWSERA activity/event		

Name and Surname

Name of the person you represent

Relationship to the above-mentioned person

Signature

Date

Ibercivis, as NEWSERA data responsible, is committed to processing information in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The personal data collected on this form will be held securely and will only be used for administrative purposes.

Your rights

You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about the person you represent and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required. You can ask Ibercivis to stop using their images/recordings at any time, in which case it will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation.

Contact details

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information please contact with Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. If you have any questions relating to data protection please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer, Francisco Sanz, tel: +34 876 55 53 96 email ethics@ibercivis.es

5.2.2 Template Consent forms for Photography/Recording (both general and vulnerable persons)

The first one is the template consent form for taking photographs and/or recordings in case of **adults** capable of giving their consent.

Template Consent form for Photography/Recording (general)

Issue	YES	NO
I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings including images of me, both internally and externally to promote the project. These images could be used in print and digital media formats including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters banners, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.		
I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in the Europe and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as Europe legislation provides.		
I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive of NEWSERA life.		
I have read and understand the conditions and consent to my images being used as described.		

Name and Surname

Signature

Date

Ibercivis, as NEWSERA data responsible, is committed to processing information in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The personal data collected on this form will be held securely and will only be used for administrative purposes.

Your rights

You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about you and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required. You can ask Ibercivis to stop using your images/recordings at any

time, in which case it will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation.

Contact details

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information please contact with Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. If you have any questions relating to data protection please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer, Francisco Sanz, tel: +34 876 55 53 96 email ethics@ibercivis.es

There is a different form in case of vulnerable persons - **children, young people or vulnerable adults** - are involved in some of the activities. This form will be completed by the legal representant of vulnerable persons.

Template Consent form for Photography/Recording (vulnerable persons)

Issue	Yes	No
I consent to the NEWSERA project using photographs and/or recordings including images of the person I represent, both internally and externally to promote the project. These images could be used in print and digital media formats including print publications, websites, e-marketing, poster banners, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.		
I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in Europe, and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as European legislation provides.		
I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive of NEWSERA life.		
I have read and understand the conditions and consent to my images being used as described.		

Name and Surname

Name of the person you represent

Relationship to the above-mentioned person

Signature

Date

Ibercivis, as NEWSERA data responsible, is committed to processing information in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The personal data collected on this form will be held securely and will only be used for administrative purposes.

Your rights

You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about the person you represent and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required. You can ask Ibercivis to stop using the images/recordings of the person you represent at any time, in which case it will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation.

Contact details

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information please contact with Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. If you have any questions relating to data protection please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer, Francisco Sanz, tel: +34 876 55 53 96 email ethics@ibercivis.es

All the forms will include the necessary information about the NEWSERA projects and its partners, at least their names and logos.

6. Annex. NEWSERA survey on ‘Science Communication through Citizen Science’: privacy notice

The corresponding document to this privacy notice is available at: https://newsera2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/NEWSERA_Survey-privacy-notice.pdf

The NEWSERA project is launching a survey about science communication strategies as performed by citizen science projects across the EU and the UK. This document presents the information related to data treatment and survey respondents rights on it.

THE SURVEY

The survey (available at <https://bit.ly/2TI3NVw>) is addressed to responsables for citizen science projects based in the EU and UK and it includes some **general information about the project and** about the ways used to **communicate and engage** with its community. The aim of the survey is to paint a clearer picture of the science communication strategies carried out by citizen science projects and to get in touch with projects to include in the **co-creation Labs** that will be organized as part of NEWSERA.

RESPONDENT RIGHTS ON DATA

How to withdraw from the project?

You are free to leave the survey at any moment. If you complete and submit the survey, you must know that all personal data are regulated under the GDPR, so you can exercise your rights according to this law. You can request the complete elimination of your data by email at ethics@ibercivis.es.

What will the information be used for?

We will not use personal data for the research. We will require personal or institutional data to keep contact, if you agree to provide us with it.

Retention schedule

Personal Data will be stored until the end of the project: December 2022.

Who is responsible for data processing

Ibercivis is responsible for processing and protecting all personal - and no personal - data obtained. Ibercivis is a non-profit private foundation with NIF: G99330094. It was created on November 14, 2011 in Madrid. Its objectives are to an EU project funded by Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program - Grant Agreement n. 873125 continue with its work of collaboration with citizen research and carry out dissemination and training activities. It has a fiscal address in Campus Río Ebro, R&D Building, C/Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. The email address for ethical issues is ethics@ibercivis.es. University of Padova (UNIPD) is also responsible for processing and protecting the survey data. Contact person at UNIPD is the researcher Paolo Giardullo paolo.giardullo@unipd.it.

Personal data transfer

We follow strict security procedures when storing personal data. Under no circumstances we will transfer personal data to third parties outside the NEWSERA Consortium.

Rights and how to exercise them

You have the right to:

- Request information about whether we have personal data about you and, if so, what information we have, why we have it and how we are using it.
- Request access to your personal data. This allows you to receive a copy of your personal data and to correct any incomplete or incorrect information we have about you.

- Request personal data deletion. This allows you to delete or ask us to delete your personal data.
- Request to transfer your personal data to you or to a third party in an electronic and structured format - commonly known as the right to data portability.
- You can exercise any of these rights through the Newsera website or by email writing to ethics@ibercivis.es.
- You will not have to pay any fee to access your personal data - or to exercise any other of your rights.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

NEWSERA is studying citizen science as a new form of science communication that can strengthen the link between science and society. We want to analyse the strategies that CS projects adopt to communicate with different targets (citizen scientists and society, academic scientists, industries, policy makers).

NEWSERA is a project that includes partners from Spain, Italy and Portugal. It's funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program, under Grant Agreement n. 873125. To learn more about the project, visit newsera2020.eu or contact us at info@newsera2020.eu

7. Annex.

Informed consent form

NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs

Data and information treatment consent for participants
in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs

Dear NEWSERA collaborator,

Thank you very much for your participation in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab,
in (place/city) _____, on (date) _____.

We care about your data and your rights on them: all personal data are regulated under the GDPR, so you can exercise your rights according to this law.

We will not use personal data for the research. We will require personal data only to keep contact with you, if you agree to provide it to us. Personal Data will be stored until the end of the project and the correspondent final report.

We follow strict security procedures when storing personal data and under no circumstances we will transfer personal data to third parties. Ibercivis is responsible for processing and protecting all personal – and no personal – data obtained.

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information, please contact the **NEWSERA's Data**

Protection Officer:

Francisco Sanz

Tel: +34 876 55 53 96

Email: ethics@ibercivis.es

Postal address: Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

To read more about data protection and how to exercise your rights on data, please read the full privacy notice on Protection Of Personal Data (POPD) attached or find it at this URL:

https://newsera2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/NEWSERA-Labs_Privacy-notice.pdf

Email address: _____

Having read the document below (POPD), please **tick the following boxes** if you agree.

- I have read the information presented in the POPD document (see the attached documentation or the link above).
- I know the possibility to ask any doubt regarding the project using face-to-face interview (offline or online) if possible, or by email at ethics@ibercivis.es.
- I consent to NEWSERA sending me information about the project by email.
- I know that I am doing voluntary contributions and I can leave the project when I want.
- I will not upload fake data with bad faith.
- I know that my personal data is regulated under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings including images of me, both internally and externally to promote the project. These images could be used in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters banners, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in Europe, and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as European legislation provides.
- I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive beyond NEWSERA life.
- I agree to take part in this project.
- I agree to my name, surname and affiliation appearing in the corresponding public report.

Signed:

Name and surname:

Informed consent, related to images and/or recordings, given by the corresponding legal representatives of minors under 14 years of age attending or present at the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab

- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings, including images of the minor I represent, as a parent or legal guardian. These images may be used both internally and externally to promote the project, in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings, including images of the child I represent, as a parent or legal guardian, **provided that in those images the child is not recognisable or identifiable in any way.** These images may be used both internally and externally to promote the project, in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in Europe, and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as European legislation provides.
- I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive beyond NEWSERA life.
- I legally represent the minor as a parent and I have the express or implied consent of the other parent to give this consent.

Signed:

Name and surname of parent or legal guardian:

Privacy notice on Protection Of Personal Data

PERSONAL DATA, PRIVACY AND PARTICIPANTS RIGHTS

We care about your data and your rights on them: all personal data are regulated under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, so you can exercise your rights according to this law.

What kind of data will we collect?

We will collect different types of data: one of them is mandatory and the rest are optional.

The mandatory fields are: first name, second name, country and email address. The optional data are the other demographic variables: gender, age, profile category and institution.

What will the information be used for?

We will use demographic data (gender, age, country, profile category and institution) only for statistical purposes. We will not use personal data for the research.

We will require personal - and optionally institutional - data to keep contact, if you agree to provide us with it.

Retention schedule

Personal Data will be stored until the end of the project and the publication of the correspondent final report: March 2023.

Who is responsible for data processing

Ibercivis is responsible for processing and protecting all personal - and no personal - data obtained. Ibercivis is a non-profit private foundation with NIF: G99330094. It was created on November 14, 2011 in Madrid. Its objectives are to continue with its work of collaboration with citizen research and carry out dissemination and training activities. It has a fiscal address in Campus Río Ebro, R&D Building, C/Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. The email address for ethical issues is ethics@ibercivis.es.

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- Request personal data deletion. This allows you to delete or ask us to delete your personal data.
- Request to transfer your personal data to you or to a third party in an electronic and structured format - commonly known as the right to data portability.
- You can exercise any of these rights through the NewsEra website or by email writing to ethics@ibercivis.es.
- You will not have to pay any fee to access your personal data - or to exercise any other of your rights.